

SAIBAGE

Sulfur-Aluminium Battery with Advanced Polymeric Gel Electrolytes

H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017

FET-Open – Novel ideas for radically new technologies

GA 766581

Type of action: RIA (Research and Innovation action)

Start date of the project: 01/11/2017

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D.2 Communication Strategy

Project partners

LOGO	Partner full name	Acronym
	Albufera Energy Storage S.L.	AES
	University of Leicester	UoL
	Scionix Ltd.	Scionix
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
	Technische Universität Graz	TUG

	University of Southampton	UoS
	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU

Deliverable Name: Communication Plan

Led by: Albufera Energy Storage

Partners: All

Date	Version	Author	Institution	Comments*
11/04/2018	01	Ana L. Cudero	AES	Creation

* Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
EBRA	European Battery Recycling Association
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance
EPBA	European Portable Battery Association
ERA	Energy Research Accelerator
EUCOBAT	European association of national collection schemes for batteries
EUROBAT	Association of European Automotive and Industrial Battery Manufacturers
IPR	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non Governmental Organization
SME	Small-medium Enterprise

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1. Introduction

The dissemination strategy presented in the present deliverable has the purpose to set the guidelines regarding dissemination and communication activities to carry out by all the participating partners along the project life.

SALBAGE is an ambitious project in terms of technological and industrial implementation with a huge potential to change and improve battery performance, this is why the correct communication of the project and its activities may have great interest not only for the R&D community, but also for the general public. The project coordinator (AES) is responsible for the implementation of the dissemination strategy. In particular, AES coordinates the dissemination actions of the project with the direct participation of the whole consortium feeding this dissemination activity with results achieved during the project. Periodically, the dissemination plan will be updated including future events and a brief summary of the events with participation of SALBAGE partners.

All the dissemination activities and events organized by the SALBAGE consortium as well as all public documents generated during the project lifetime will be made available through the public project website www.salbageproject.eu, in accordance with this document and the Data Management Plan (D1.3). Dissemination and communication activities will be updated periodically during the project lifetime, and updated versions of this report may be released at due time.

2. Objectives

The communication strategy will be the roadmap for getting the project activities across to the target audience. This plan is to be seen as an essential tool of marketing and public relations management. In this context, communication needs to translate the science into a language into messages that are understood by non-experts.

As a main objective of the communication plan the dissemination activities will be focused in improving the public awareness carried out with the general purpose of making SALBAGE project known. Periodically updating its progress and informing about its progress will help us to approach it to public opinion. Special importance will be dedicated to the need of spreading the results and project knowledge amongst general public. R&D European community as well as the energy industry related organizations will be prioritized boosting exchange between them and politics, NGOs and the general public.

According to the EU regulatory requirements on communication and dissemination, our objective will also ensure compliance with FET-Open program guarantying the transparency during the implementation of the project.

In favour of efficient coordination and cooperation within whole consortium, the dissemination campaign will be outlined during the project providing an indicative timeline for each activity.

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3. Target Groups/ Audience

SALBAGE dissemination activities are focussed, as main audience, on the European Research and Scientific communities as well as potential stakeholders within the industry. However, other communities are also targeted due to its potential interest in the project results. Therefore, the identified audience of the project will be the following:

- Research groups working in batteries and electrochemistry
- Research centers (academic and non-academic)
- Local government officials
- Environmental/ Recycling organizations (EPBA, EUROBAT, EBRA and Eucobat) and recycling companies (Ecopilas-Recyclia, Umicore, Akkuser, SNAM, Accurec and uRecycle)
- European institution involved in Research and Innovation
- NGOs such as industry associations
- Societal engaged actors: experts, info providers, end-users...
- Energy storage SME's
- Media representatives
- Policy makers, regulators and standardization groups as EERA and recently created European Battery Alliance.
- International energy storage organizations as EASE
- General public

4. Image and layout

Common graphic identity in the dissemination activities allows a better recognition that helps creating a project identity, in order to make easier to identify the “project brand”. This visual identity includes a logo and a colour scheme both for the website and for printed materials.

4.1. Logo

A logo has been created and proper templates prepared and shared with the partner Figure 1 presents the logo:

Figure 1: SALBAGE Logo

The logo features a direct linking with a battery, using soft and harmonious pantones: green, related environmentally friendly materials, whereas in grey it highlights an “Al” typeface to attract attention towards the Aluminum component being the rest of the letters in yellowish orange matching the colour of Sulphur.

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4.2. Templates

Common layouts for SALBAGE dissemination activities (posters, website, presentations, reports..) will be used in order to keep an uniform project image. Word and PowerPoint templates have been uploaded to the intranet for the partners to use in its internal (and towards the EU) reporting and also in external presentations (conferences, etc).

4.3. Language

The official language of the SALBAGE project is English. Thus, all the dissemination material generated by the project will be available in English language. If a project partners require dissemination materials in other languages, they must carry the cost of translation by themselves.

5. Dissemination channels

The progress and outcomes of the project will be disseminated in a variety of ways to ensure maximum coverage and sharing of information, expertise and experience. All partners will be involved in knowledge transfer, in order to reach as large an audience as possible. A combination of dissemination methods will be used to reach out to all relevant sectors, including: politics, science, industry and the general public. Therefore, dissemination activities will be structured at four levels:

- (i) Dissemination to scientific community
- (ii) Organization of workshops and conferences
- (iii) Dissemination to policy makers, NGO and general public (website, social networks, press releases and other events...)
- (iv) Dissemination to industry

5.1. Dissemination to the scientific community

5.1.1. Congresses

Scientific results will be disseminated in national and international conferences. Table 1 shows some of the tentative conferences where SALBAGE partners could present to the scientific community their most relevant results related to the project.

Table 1: (Foreseen) participation at conferences and workshops

Event description	Audience	Attendants	Involvement
69th, 70th and 71th Annual meetings of ISE (International Society of Electrochemistry)	Scientific, Industry	>1000	Oral/poster presentation
Meetings of The Electrochemical Society (2018-2020)	Scientific, Industry	>1000	Oral/poster presentation
March Meeting of the American Chemis Society (2019)	Scientific, Industry	>1000	Oral/poster presentation

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International Workshop on Computational Design and Discovery of Novel Materials COMDI 2018.	Scientific	>200	Oral/poster presentation
IDA Universe Talks April and September 2018	Outreach (Science Popularization))	100	Oral Presentation
10th (2018) and 11th (2020) ECNP International Conference on Nanostructured Polymers and Nanocomposites	Scientific	>250	Keynote/Oral/poster presentation
Metal Advanced Batteries International Conference (MABIC) 2020	Science, Industry, Policy makers	>150	Oral/poster presentation Organization

5.1.2. Scientific publications

It is expected at least 2 scientific publications per academic partner per year. Some of journals where the papers can be potentially published include: *Nature Energy*, *Science Advances*, *ACS Nano*, *Advanced Energy Materials*, *Nano Letters*, *Nanoscale*, *Journal of Energy Storage*, *Journal of Power Sources*, *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, *Journal of the Electrochemical Society*, *Electrochimica Acta*, *ACS Materials and Interfaces*, *ACS Energy Letters*, *Chemical Science*, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, *Physical Review Letters*. Being all of them top-level peer-review journals.

5.1.3. Others

SALBAGE project might also produce output in form of PhD and Master Thesis. Table 2 displays the foreseen output of PhD and Master Theses by partner

Table 2: Expected output of PhD and Master Theses by partner

SALBAGE Partner	Number of Master Thesis	Number of PhD Thesis
UoL	2	0
CSIC	2/3	1/2
TUG	1	2
UoS	0	1
DTU	1	0

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The new IPR generated will be managed to ensure that any foreground is properly protected before any dissemination on those results is generated. The Consortium Agreement addresses the framework and procedures to be followed by the project partners which intention will be to maximize opportunities for effective collaboration and exploitation.

SALBAGE consortium will ensure that all the scientific publications resulting from the project will be granted Open Access according to the Project Data Management Plan (D1.3). Following the Dissemination Strategy of the H2020 framework, a combination of Gold and Green Access Strategy will be implemented. This will ensure that the results will be open to the scientific community and will reach the largest possible number of individuals.

5.2. Organization of Workshops and Conferences

SALBAGE consortium will organize one workshop and two summer schools along the project. A special course on Novel energy storage systems (M22) will be organized by DTU focused on raising awareness of young researchers towards the new energy storage technology challenges.

In addition, a seminar on Technology Transfer will be coordinated by UoL and Scionix in M18.

In the last year of the project, the Metal-Advanced Batteries International Conference “MaBIC” that AES organizes annually will include a special workshop devoted to SALBAGE project (M32). This workshop will be open to all battery research scientific community with the aim to discuss the main results obtained along SALBAGE project in the development of Aluminium-Sulfur battery besides major findings in other battery technologies by means of selected talks and posters.

5.3. Dissemination to general public, policy makers and NGO

5.3.1. Website

A dedicated project website has been established at the beginning of the project (M2). AES is the responsible of it, providing uninterruptedly maintenance and refinement during the project life. The Project Website is hosted at www.salbageproject.eu. It also includes a private area to host all non-public deliverables and to be used for all collaboration activities within the project by partners and EC where all the necessary project data, reporting templates, etc will be uploaded.

This website acts as central information channel for the wider public and the project’s participants and it will be periodically updated with the progresses of the Aluminium-Sulfur battery according to each WP accomplishments. As a main channel for dissemination of the project and its progress, it works as a landing page for many of the communication actions indicated in the dissemination plan, since it contains open sections such as: project and consortium information, news and events, etc.

The project website has the following structure:

- HOME : welcomes the visitor and provides a brief summary of the project. It also includes the obliged reference to the European Funded project as well as EU logo and GA. Number.
- SALBAGE PROJECT: the project summary and scope is provided here
- PARTNERS: partners logos and direct links to their webpages can be found here
- NEWS/EVENTS: all the information regarding participation of the partners in events as well as any news (project meetings, progress, etc) will be published here

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- MEDIA/DOWNLOADS: public documents will, newsletters, etc will be hosted here.
- CONTACT: data contact can be found here.

The page has the means to measure parameters such as number of visits, traffic of the web, etc by means of the tool **Advanced Web Statistics 7.6**, and just during the present month it has had life 362 visits, as can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 2. Statistics of the Salbageproject.eu webpage.

5.3.2. Social networks

SALBAGE project has set up profiles in LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/salbage-project-fetopen/>) and Twitter (: <https://www.twitter.com/SALBAGE Project>).

With more and more people joining social media sites and using them regularly, the social media coverage is becoming unquestionable. Their use allows to reach wider public with audiences beyond the project’s own community. The use of social network will include announcements to the general public of project meetings, attendance of the partners to workshops and conferences, news and radio/television interviews mentioning SALBAGE project and announcements of any new and/or event what could be potentially relevant to the development of SALBAGE project.

A direct link to LinkedIn and Twitter channels of the project will be found at SALBAGE project website.

Additionally, the Promotion and Science Dissemination Department of the ICTP-CSIC (<http://www.ictp.csic.es/ICTP2/es/divulgacion>) is devoted to knowledge transfer and dissemination of the activities of the ICTP researchers at all levels, including social networks, which will be used for the communication of SALBAGE activities (<https://www.facebook.com/ICTP-Instituto-de-Ciencia-y-Tecnología-de-Polímeros-315834901804788/>, https://twitter.com/ictp_promocion, <https://www.youtube.com/user/InfoCTP>).

The University of Southampton has a Communications and Marketing team as part of the professional services departments. The University of Southampton is also present in social networks such as Facebook (<https://en-gb.facebook.com/unisouthampton/>). The department of chemistry of Southampton is also present in social networks such as Facebook

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(<https://www.facebook.com/UoSChemistry>). All these channels will be also used to communicate the different SALBAGE activities.

5.3.3. Other events, newsletters and press releases

The SALBAGE consortium will produce a newsletter in electronic format every year in English Language. National language translation of each periodic e-Newsletter shall be performed by the partners if relevant. The e-Newsletters will be posted in the project website and all publications will be downloadable from there.

We will also release information about the different actions around the project. Press releases help project get valuable publicity for spreading far and wide the message by boosting its visibility. We are planning press releases for important achievements during the course of the project which will be focused on the completion of a major milestone as well as by the end of the project.

Furthermore, we plan to participate in Science Fairs and events such as European Researchers' Night as well as Open Days for school visits to bring researchers closer to the general public and to increase awareness of research and innovation activities about batteries and specifically about the development of Aluminium-Sulfur battery.

As for the other partners, the Promotion and Science Dissemination Department of the ICTP-CSIC designs and develops dissemination sources such as the digital Newsletter InfoICTP, which will be used to communicate relevant SALBAGE news.

Moreover, the department of Chemistry of Southampton also have a dedicated team for the promotion and dissemination of achievements of projects as SALBAGE. The department of Chemistry produces a Chemistry Newsletter and has a dedicated webpages to disseminate important news (<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/chemistry/news/latest.page>), seminars (<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/chemistry/news/seminars/latest.page>) and events (<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/chemistry/news/events/latest.page>). The University of Southampton participates and organizes several important outreach events such as the Science and Engineering day (<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/per/university/festival/science-and-engineering-day.page>) where SALBAGE project will be disseminated.

5.4. Dissemination to industry

Without prejudice that the actions outlined in Section 5.2 (organization of workshops and seminars) and Section 5.3 (website, social networks, press releases and e-new letters) will also contribute to the dissemination of the SALBAGE project results to stakeholders from industry, more specific and proactive actions are planned to ensure that broad industry awareness and support are achieved. These activities include:

- Participation of industrial partners of the project (AES and Scionix) in industry/technology fairs

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- Participation in EASE network and new European Battery Alliance with the aim of obtaining specific dissemination and collaboration with key industrial partners

The project will also benefit from ERA dissemination mechanisms. This is an organization, to which is one of the project partners (UoL) belongs to, that supports research and development in new battery chemistry. This is collaboration between several Universities, the UK Government and several corporations what allows a direct contact with companies with interest in energy e.g. Jaguar-Landrover, Alstom, TWI.

In addition, and related to the polymer industry, the Promotion and Science Dissemination Department of the ICTP-CSIC designs and develops dissemination sources such as the journal *Revista de Plásticos Modernos* (<http://www.revistaplasticosmodernos.es>) founded in 1950, well known to the industrial partners of ICTP-CSIC in Spain and South America.

Communications and Marketing team of the University of Southampton manages the University's reputation and brand. They communicate its aims and achievements to stakeholders around the world including SALBAGE project achievements.

6. Impact evaluation

Evaluating the success of dissemination and communication efforts is an iterative process. Once we have begun the process of dissemination, it will be interesting to evaluate the effect that our dissemination strategies have on getting our message. Dissemination is not a one-time activity; rather, it is a long-term relationship that will provide ongoing feedback to help us improve our message.

Table 3 shows a summary of the principal KPIs to evaluate the results of the communication plan, and their impact on the different audiences.

Table 3: Summary of KPIs to monitor and evaluate the different dissemination activities

METHOD	IMPLEMENTATION	RESULT INDICATORS	IMPACT INDICATORS	TARGET GROUP	LEAD PARTICIPANT
WEBSITE	Public/Private area Downloads section Data Bases	Qty of users/visit Qty of downloaded doc Qty of pages visited	Knowing how much traffic a website gets helps us validate the website's content.	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	AES
SOCIAL NETWORKS (Twitter/LinkedIn)	Open profiles	Qty of social followers	Social networking has become powerful marketing and communication tools.	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	AES

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SEMINARS, CONFERENCE, FAIRS, WORKSHOP	N° of events organized N° of events attended	Qty of responses to invitations Qty of attendees: Qty of requests for further information	Present an excellent opportunity to discuss their work and provides an important channel for exchange of information between them. Attendance is a good tester to evaluate the success of every event.	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	All
SUMMER SCHOOLS	1 Summer School organized	Qty of attendees	The value of attendance at a summer school has also positive repercussions on future professional career making student CV stand out from the crowd.	Scientific Public	DTU
MASS MEDIA PARTNERSHIP	N° of press release TV coverage Radio coverage	Qty of press interviews Qty of TV interviews Qty of radio interviews Qty of Press releases issued	The best way to measure the effectiveness of a press release is knowing how many media and people have echoed the distributed news and, consequently, the clipping impact generated from these mentions.	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	AES
NEWSLETTER	N° of newsletter published	Qty of subscribers Qty of Open Rate	The Open Rate for an email campaign is a measure of how many recipients viewed your email	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	AES
PUBLICATIONS	N° of publications	Impact factor of the Journal N of citations	Impact factor indicator to assess the quality of researchers publications	Scientific Public	All
OPEN DAYS FOR SCHOOL VISITS	N° of events organized	Qty of responses to invitations Qty of attendees: anticipated number – actual number Qty of requests for further information		Scientific Public	All
EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS' NIGHT	N° of events organized	Qty of attendees: anticipated number – actual number Qty of requests for further information	Aims to bring researchers closer to the general public and to increase awareness of research and innovation activities.	All target groups, (general public, scientific public potential beneficiaries, beneficiaries...)	All

7. Dissemination rules

There are some general rules that the dissemination activities must follow, according to the EU regulations and the Grant Agreement. They are the following:

7.1. General rules

- **Obligation to disseminate the results:** according to article 29.1 of GA: “Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium)”.

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- **Obligation to inform to other partners:** according to article 29.1 of GA: “A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate”.
- **Obligation of open access to research data and scientific publications:** the data management life cycle for all research data and scientific publications generated by the project partners is described at Data Management Plan of SALBAGE project (Deliverable 1.3)

7.2. EU visual identity

Visibility of EU funding: unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, and in accordance with the European Commission visual identity¹, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must comply with the following:

- (a) display the EU emblem as shown in figure3, that can be downloaded from the EU official webpage.

Figure 3 EU official Logo

- (b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 766581”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Finally, and according to article 29.5 of GA, “any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/resources-partners/european-commission-visual-identity_en

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